

Placeholder Name of the conference

Placeholder Session title

© Authors. This work is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License

NFDI4Immuno and AIRR Knowledge Commons: Building Complementary FAIR Infrastructures for Immunological Data

Ulrik Stervbo¹ <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-1617-8244>, on behalf of NFDI4Immuno and AKC

¹ Ruhr University Bochum, Bochum, Germany

² German Cancer Research Center (DKFZ), Heidelberg, Germany

³ University of Texas Southwestern Medical Center, Dallas, Texas, United States

*Correspondence: Ulrik Stervbo, ulrik.stervbo@elisabethgruppe.de

Abstract

The field of immunology generates diverse and complex datasets that require interoperable and well-structured research data infrastructures. NFDI4Immuno and the AIRR Knowledge Commons (AKC) address this challenge from complementary perspectives, each focusing on standardization and adherence to the FAIR principles. Despite their overlapping interests, these two consortia currently operate with different metadata models. Here, we present our approach for developing alignment strategies between these infrastructures to improve interoperability.

NFDI4Immuno, established as part of the German National Research Data Infrastructure (NFDI), is developing a federated repository ecosystem tailored to the broader immunological data landscape. The consortium builds robust metadata models, automated data pipelines, and modular software stacks to support a variety of data types with a substantial initial focus on Adaptive Immune Receptor Repertoire sequencing (AIRR-seq) data and integration into the AIRR Data Commons (ADC).

The AIRR Knowledge Commons (AKC), funded by the U.S. National Institute of Allergy and Infectious Diseases (NIAID), focuses specifically on immunoglobulin (Ig) and T cell receptors (TCR) and integrates data from globally recognized, community-driven repositories such as those in the ADC, the Immune Epitope Database (IEDB), the Immune Receptor Antigen Database (IRAD), and VDJbase. AKC brings together information Ig/TCR sequences, gene polymorphisms, and antigen specificities.

We will present an analysis of the current metadata models used by both infrastructures, highlighting areas of overlap and divergence. Our work examines potential points of integration between AKC's immune receptor-specific model and NFDI4Immuno's broader immunological data framework. We will propose strategies for metadata mapping that respect the different scopes while identifying opportunities for enhanced interoperability.

By exploring alignment possibilities between these complementary infrastructures across institutional and national boundaries, we aim to identify pathways toward reducing barriers

between and within research communities and to facilitate data reuse across scientific domains.

Keywords: Data Interoperability, Immunological Repositories, FAIR Principles

Resources

ADC: <https://www.antibodysociety.org/the-airr-community/airr-data-commons/>

AKC: <https://airr-knowledge.org/>

IEDB: <https://www.iedb.org/>

IRAD: <http://irad.roskinlab.org/>

VDJbase: <https://vdjbase.org/>

Author contributions

All authors contributed to the conceptualization, writing - original draft and writing - review & editing.

Competing interests

The authors declare that they have no competing interests.

Funding

NFDI4Immuno is funded by DFG, grant number 501875662. AKC is funded by NIAID, grant number U24AI177622.

Acknowledgement

If you want to acknowledge persons or institutions you can do so here.

References